

Metal Complexes with Sulphur Donor Ligands-I. Preparation and Characterisation of Some Mixed Ligand Complexes Containing Bidentate Tertiary Amines and Ethyl Xanthate

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Mixed ligand complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) containing ethyl xanthate and 1,10 phenanthroline or 2, 2' bipyridyl have been prepared through a two step process. In the first step $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ is prepared which in the second step on interaction with ethylxanthate results in the replacement of the four water molecules by two xanthate molecules. The composition of the complexes has been determined by radiometric, amperometric and potentiometric titrations and by chemical analysis of the isolated complexes. Infrared spectra show the binding of the xanthate and 1,10 phenanthroline or 2, 2' bipyridyl to the metal.

THE increasing commercial value of transition metal complexes of xanthates and dithiocarbamates has aroused considerable interest in their chemistry. While their analytical applications are well known¹⁻³, they are now finding extensive use in vulcanisation of rubber, froth floatation process for concentration of sulphide ores, as antioxidants, lubricants⁴⁻⁷ and have been found to possess fungicidal and insecticidal activity⁸. Although a large amount of work has been carried out on the simple metal xanthates, little attention has been paid to their mixed ligand complexes in spite of the fact that introduction of another ligand generally increases their fungicidal and insecticidal activity to a considerable extent. An attempt has thus been made to prepare some mixed ligand complexes of ethyl xanthate and 1,10 phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2' bipyridyl (bipy).

Experimental

Reagent grade (S. Merck) 1,10 phenanthroline, 2,2' bipyridyl and potassium ethyl xanthate were used as received without any further purification. The metals were reagent grade BDH products.

Preparation of the complexes :

In order to prepare the desired complexes, a two step process was adopted. In the first step, the metal complexes with 1,10 phenanthroline and 2,2' bipyridyl of the type $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ were prepared by the method adopted by Parikh and Bhattacharya⁹ (LN_2 denotes phen or bipy). In the first step, in a typical preparation of the copper complex, a mixture of 2 mM of 1,10 phenanthroline in 10 cm³ of ethanol and 2 mM of $CuCl_2$ in 10 cm³ of water was refluxed for about 45 min on a water bath. On cooling and adding excess of absolute

ethyl alcohol, a green complex was precipitated which was suction filtered and washed with ice-cold 50% ethanol. The crude product was dissolved in a minimum quantity of hot 50% ethanol and recrystallised by slow cooling to 0° followed by addition of excess absolute ethanol. The product was dried under vacuum over anhydrous calcium chloride. Analysis of the dried product corresponded to $[Cu(phen)(H_2O)_4]Cl_2$. Similarly complexes were prepared from $ZnSO_4$, $CdSO_4$, $NiSO_4$, $MnSO_4$ and $CoSO_4$ and 2,2' bipyridyl.

In the second step, 1 mM of the above complex was dissolved in 10 cm³ of water and to this 20 cm³ of an aqueous solution containing 2 mM of potassium ethyl xanthate was added dropwise with magnetic stirring. A brick red precipitate of $[Cu(phen)(xan)_2]$ was obtained which was suction filtered, washed with 20% ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Composition of the complexes :

The composition of the complexes was determined by amperometric, potentiometric and radiometric titrations.

Amperometric titrations in 0.1M K_2SO_4 were carried out at potentials lying either on the plateaux of the polarograms of potassium ethyl xanthate or the complex $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$. 0.005% gelatin was used as maxima suppressor in the case of copper-bipyridyl-xanthate complex only. Nitrogen was bubbled through the solutions in the polarographic cell for about 15 min before commencing the titration and then for 5 min after each addition of the titrant. Current was then measured after allowing the solution to stand for 2 minutes. The current was measured with Toshniwal manual

polarograph (type CLO-2A) used in conjunction with a Pye scalamp galvanometer. The capillary characteristic was found to be $1.77 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out by taking 40 cm^3 of $0.002M$ of potassium ethyl xanthate solution in the cell and titrating against $0.02M$ $[\text{M}(\text{LN}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$. In the case of $[\text{Cd}(\text{phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ a solution of $0.001M$ xanthate was titrated against $0.01M$ $[\text{Cd}(\text{phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$. The solutions were magnetically stirred for 1 min after each addition of the titrant and allowed to stand for 2 min before recording the potential. The potential was further checked twice after an interval of 1 min each. Reverse titrations were not successful and gave erratic results. For determining the inflection points, both the first derivative ($\Delta E/\Delta V$) and the second derivative ($\Delta^2 E/\Delta V^2$) were plotted against the volume of the titrant. The potential was measured using a Toshniwal portable potentiometer using an external galvanometer with a lamp and scale arrangement. A silver-silver sulphide electrode and a saturated calomel electrode were used as indicator and reference electrodes respectively. The silver-silver sulphide electrode was prepared as described¹¹.

Radiometric titrations were carried out by preparing labelled $[\text{M}^*(\text{LN}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ using radioisotopes of cobalt, zinc, manganese and cadmium and titrating against potassium ethyl xanthate. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out using a concentration of about $0.02M$ of the reagents as previously described¹⁰. Radioisotopes, Co^{58} , Zn^{65} , Mn^{54} and Cd^{115m} as carrier free samples were obtained from the Bhabha Atomic Research Establishment, Trombay, India in the form of their chlorides in HCl solution (activity 0.5 to 2.0 mCi/ml). 0.2 to 1.0 cm^3 of the active sample was diluted to 30 cm^3 with the inactive solution ($0.2M$) of the same metal ion, which was then used to prepare $[\text{M}^*(\text{LN}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$. The activity of the solutions was measured with a γ -ray scintillation spectrometer employing a NaI(Tl) crystal. In the case of the cadmium complex the activity was measured using a Geiger Muller counter since Cd^{115m} is a β -emitter.

Chemical analysis :

The metal content of the complexes was determined after decomposing the sample by prolonged boiling with concentrated nitric acid. Excess HNO_3 was removed by slow heating after adding a few drops of conc. H_2SO_4 . The solution was cooled, diluted to about 20 cm^3 with distilled water and made up to 100 cm^3 after transferring to a measuring flask. Manganese was estimated as permanganate after oxidation with periodate, nickel with dimethyl glyoxime and copper with diethyldithiocarbamate spectrophotometrically¹². Zinc, cadmium and cobalt were estimated gravimetrically with dihydrogen ammonium phosphate

and α -nitroso β -naphthol respectively¹². For spectrophotometric determinations, about 20 mg of the sample was used while for the gravimetric estimation, about 200 mg was taken.

Sulphur content of the complexes was determined after decomposing about 200 mg of the compound by refluxing for about 4 h with 0.5 g of KOH and 1.5 g of KMnO_4 in 100 ml of H_2O whereby the sulphur content of the complex was converted to SO_4^{2-} . The sulphate ions were estimated gravimetrically after precipitation as BaSO_4 with BaCl_2 .

Carbon and nitrogen were estimated by the standard microanalytical methods.

Infrared spectra :

Infrared spectra of the complexes in the range 4000 - 240 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Beckmann IR 20 spectrophotometer. The infrared spectra in the range 600 - 240 cm^{-1} were obtained as nujol mulls on polyethylene plates and in the range 4000 - 600 cm^{-1} in KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies show that xanthate on interaction with the complex $[\text{M}(\text{LN}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$ replaces the four water molecules of the complex to give $[\text{M}(\text{LN}_2)(\text{xan})_2]$. These observations find support from the results of amperometric, potentiometric and radiometric titrations.

In the direct radiometric titrations (with potassium ethyl xanthate as titrant), the activity

Fig. 1. Radiometric titrations.

(a) Direct titration :

- (I) 4.0 cm^3 of $0.02M$ $[\text{Mn}(\text{Phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{SO}_4$ against $0.08M$ Xanthate
- (II) 2.0 cm^3 of $0.02M$ $[\text{Co}(\text{Bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{SO}_4$ against $0.02M$ Xanthate

(b) Reverse titration :

- (III) 2.0 cm^3 of $0.08M$ Xanthate against $0.02M$ $[\text{Mn}(\text{Phen})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{SO}_4$
- (IV) 4.0 cm^3 of $0.02M$ Xanthate against $0.02M$ $[\text{Co}(\text{Bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{SO}_4$

shows a continuous decrease. The rate of decrease is rapid in the beginning and shows a fall as the titration proceeds. The inflection point (Typical curves, Fig. 1) corresponds to the complete substitution of the four water molecules by two xanthate molecules. In the reverse titrations (with the active metal complex $[M^*(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ as titrant) the activity shows a slow increase in the beginning and then a rapid increase in activity as the titration proceeds (Typical curves, Fig. 1). The inflection point corresponds to the formation of a 1:2 complex. Since only one inflection point is observed in both the direct and reverse titrations corresponding to a 1:2 complex, the four water molecules of $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ are replaced either simultaneously by two xanthate molecules or the complex $[M(LN_2)(xan)(H_2O)_2]^+$ if formed is very unstable and reacts very rapidly with another xanthate molecule to give the final product. The continuous increase or decrease in activity points towards a reversible reaction between the complex $[M(LN_2)(H_2O)_4]^{2+}$ and xanthate represented by the following equation :

Radiometric titrations with the Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes could not be carried out due to the lack of their isotopes.

Amperometric titrations (both direct and reverse) show the formation of only 1:2 complexes (Typical curves, Fig. 2). The continuous increase or decrease in the current support the above mentioned reversible reaction.

Fig. 2. Amperometric titrations.
(a) Direct titrations :
(I) 10.0 cm³ of 0.001M [Cu(Phen)(H₂O)₄]Cl₂ against 0.01M Xanthate
(II) 20.0 cm³ of 0.002M Xanthate against 0.02M [Co(Bipy)(H₂O)₄]SO₄
(b) Reverse titrations :
(III) 20.0 cm³ of 0.001M Xanthate against 0.01M [Cu(Phen)(H₂O)₄]Cl₂
(IV) 10.0 cm³ of 0.002M [Co(Bipy)(H₂O)₄]SO₄ against 0.02M Xanthate

Potentiometric titrations also show the formation of 1:2 complexes (Typical curves, Fig. 3). These studies further show that a silver-silver sulphide electrode can be successfully used to monitor the activity of sulphur containing ligands like xanthates and dithiocarbamates.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations.
(I) 20.0 cm³ of 0.001M Xanthate against 0.01M Cd(Phen)(H₂O)₄SO₄
(II) 40.0 cm³ of 0.002M Xanthate against 0.02M [Cd(Bipy)(H₂O)₄]SO₄

Chemical analysis of the isolated products (Table 1) corresponds to the composition $[M(LN_2)(xan)_2]$, where M = Cu(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Mn(II) or Co(II), which confirms the results obtained above.

Infrared spectral data show the coordination of the metal to xanthate and 1,10 phenanthroline or 2,2' bipyridyl. The (M-N) band¹⁸ for the complexes with Co(II) and Cd(II) appears between 320 and 340 cm⁻¹ while with Mn(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) the band^{15,16} is observed between 250-300 cm⁻¹. The other ring stretching vibrations of the ligand LN₂ appearing in the range of 1600-1400 cm⁻¹ confirm the presence of this ligand in the complexes.

Potassium ethyl xanthate is also a bidentate ligand and binds through both its sulphur atoms. Three canonical forms of the xanthate complex can be visualised¹, viz.,

The infrared spectra does not show any band which can be assigned exclusively to a C=S fre-

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	%metal		%S		%C		%N	
	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd
[Mn(phen)(xan) ₂]	11.4	11.5	26.6	26.9	45.4	45.3	5.6	5.9
[Mn(bipy)(xan) ₂]	12.0	12.1	28.2	28.3	42.6	42.4	6.1	6.2
[Co(phen)(xan) ₂]	12.3	12.2	26.5	26.6	44.8	44.9	5.9	5.8
[Co(bipy)(xan) ₂]	12.7	12.9	28.2	28.0	42.1	42.0	6.0	6.1
[Ni(phen)(xan) ₂]	12.2	12.2	26.3	26.2	45.0	44.9	5.8	5.9
[Ni(bipy)(xan) ₂]	12.9	12.8	27.8	28.0	42.1	42.0	6.3	6.1
[Cu(phen)(xan) ₂]	13.2	13.1	26.2	26.4	44.4	44.5	5.6	5.8
[Cu(bipy)(xan) ₂]	13.7	13.8	27.9	27.6	41.8	41.6	6.2	6.1
[Zn(phen)(xan) ₂]	13.5	13.4	26.3	26.4	44.0	44.2	5.8	5.7
[Zn(bipy)(xan) ₂]	14.3	14.1	27.8	27.6	40.4	40.5	6.2	6.0
[Cd(phen)(xan) ₂]	21.2	21.0	23.8	24.0	40.6	40.4	5.2	5.3
[Cd(bipy)(xan) ₂]	21.8	22.0	25.4	25.1	37.8	37.6	5.8	5.5

quency. Further, the spectra shows bands in the 1120 cm^{-1} , 810 cm^{-1} and 620 cm^{-1} regions which can be assigned to the (C-S) absorptions^{17,18} while the (C-O) frequency¹⁸⁻²⁰ appears in the 1250 cm^{-1} region. It is thus feasible to assume that the canonical form [C] makes a significant contribution to the overall structure. The (M-S) absorption^{18,21} appearing in the 390 cm^{-1} region confirms the bonding of the xanthate through its sulphur atom to the metal.

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